

TEACHERS' PERCEPTION OF PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT AT SECONDARY SCHOOL LEVEL: A QUALITATIVE STUDY

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Abstract:

Professional development is the most effective and powerful skill to increase the learners' needs and then make them able to acquire these tools to complete their learning criteria. It works to fulfill the requirement of a teacher to meet with the effective teaching styles. This study aims to examine the secondary school teachers' perceptions about professional development, its importance in teaching practices and why it has been declared an instrument to get the students' learning outcomes. For this purpose, we opted semi-structured interviews for the collection of data. The total 13 participants participated in this study. The findings of the study revealed that the professional development affects teacher's classroom practices and enhances the learning achievement of students. The findings also showed that the continuous professional development induces teachers to improve their teaching competencies to meet the need of learners as per educational demands and the relevance of teacher efficacy for their effectiveness, as related to powerful CPD experiences. Moreover, school embedded professional learning opportunities can thus answer to self-direct desires for instructional change, which

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afterwards provide the motivational efforts to sustain and overcome the hurdles. Further, discussion and suggestions are given.

Keywords: professional development; continuous professional development; secondary schools; teachers' perceptions

1. Introduction

Professional development is the most effective and powerful technique to increase learners' achievements and make them able to acquire these tools to complete their learning criteria. In the contemporary situation, it has become very vital to help young people to learn the most complex and analytical skills what 21st century demands from them. Besides, it is obligatory for teachers to learn the ways that develop higher-order thinking, performance and creativity (Franke & Kazemi, 2001). The modern epoch has fully changed the previous educational system. In these days, education is based upon varieties of knowledge and skills which can not be delivered without use of professional development and understanding of what would be the teaching strategy to meet with these demands. In addition to these abrupt changes, the second most important part is cohesive to teachers that how they would satisfy the sitting students in classroom. For this, professional development induces teachers to learn these strategies and improve students' achievement through professional thinking. Likewise, an educationalist Jean Piaget (1945) worked on the same concerned aspect who afterwards concluded that the professional development makes easy these following aspects including; improving school performance, surety of classroom instruction and support the implementation of new initiatives. Additionally, the important point that leads to complete the above aspects is to get the basic concept of professional development and its best way of implementation in educational premise.

Teaching and professional development are closely adhered to each other. It kills two birds with one stone. On the one hand, it induces teachers to utilize their teaching skills for completion of learners demands, while, on the other hand, it persuades them to use qualitative skills while teaching. Guskey and Sparks (1996) used a model that organizes many components, roles, and relationships within a school's 'sphere of influence'. Their model proposed that the student's learning outcomes are improved through the complex relationships among; quality staff development, administrators, teachers, parents' knowledge, practices, and a number of factors influencing each of these components. In addition to this, it has been argued that the teacher should have to know that how students' perceptions can be merged in advance learning, as well as what should be a criterion to furnish them in each aspect of educational and professional life. In this circumstance of both teacher and students' needs, the professional development is one and everything that maintains the advancement of knowledge, teacher's abilities and student's professional life, role of administration to provide this type of

circumstances, highlights the role of friendly relation among parents, teachers and students as well as an implementation of practical teaching in classroom.

Professional development is a strategy that helps the teacher to learn that how he/she can teach as the need of learner and requirement of subject. According to Angriest and Lavvy (2001) professional development is defined as an *“any activity that increases the knowledge and skills and understanding of teachers and their effectiveness in educational institutes”*. This makes another definition of professional development that is a comprehensive, ongoing and a wide approach which helps instructors to improve their teaching style and provide them with skills to make students creative, perform better, and achieve positive outcomes. While, reality is much different from predictions because it is not that much applicable in our country in general, particularly in the concerned province. Except, Balochistan, this strategy has been applied in the developed areas of Pakistan, which showed satisfactory results in the learning and teaching environment. Many people argue that the demolished education is due to unavailability of professional development for teachers in Balochistan. The above arguments conclude the theme of this study at district Khuzdar, Balochistan, which has assented as big district of Balochistan, Pakistan, but ever remained back in the competition of education. The following questions were outlined to guide the study:

- 1) Is there any professional development planning for teachers at secondary level education in Khuzdar, Balochistan?
- 2) Whether the teachers are aware of the basic concept and need of professional development for teaching at secondary level teaching in Khuzdar, Balochistan?
- 3) How can continuing professional development courses impact and enhance teachers' classroom practices?

2. Brief Context of the District Khuzdar

Balochistan is one of the largest provinces of Pakistan that covers almost 43% of the territory. While, district Khuzdar is considered as the largest district of the province. That was established in 1st March 1974, and can be called *“Heart of Balochistan”*.

The developed and undeveloped areas in Balochistan are not big as compared to other province and this variation is due to scarcity of water and abundance of arid and wastelands. District Khuzdar is an important part of Balochistan, Pakistan which is situated on the National Highway linking Pakistan with Iran and Afghanistan. According to district development profile (1995), Khuzdar is an oldest and largest district of Balochistan, consisting of 43,200 sq. km, containing more than five Tehsils in its territory. The education sector in the district comprises of both public and private schools with varying quality. A total of 657 schools are operated in the public sector which comprise of primary, middle and high schools. 88% of these schools are in rural areas and 12% in urban areas. According to another official statically annual report (2011), the entire proportion of schools are 429, where 386 boys and 43 girls' schools are running in this large territorial district.

In addition, with the annotation of schools, the literacy rate of district Khuzdar, Balochistan is displaying a deprived status, which is just under 45%. Having 30% boys and remaining girls' education. While, many reasons have been laid for the meagre educational situation likewise, insufficient budget allocation for education that is scarcely enough for quality improvement of education such as teacher training, curriculum development, supervision and mentoring (Faiz, 2015). As this, it is very difficult to determine the implementation of professional development training teachers about their profession where they lack basic teaching requirements etc.

The historical damages of education clearly enunciate that the teachers in both educational sectors, public and private are not that much aware about the subject demands and a creative learning environment. This reason induced me to design this study that could find out the main hurdles and status quo and status query of teaching by using professional development in district Khuzdar, Balochistan. Moreover, the designed areas of this finding will be; Status quo and status quarry of teacher's using professional development, weaknesses and solutions, professionalism of teachers and its benefits, as well as in what ways the professional development can ameliorate the learning and teaching circumstances in a classroom.

3. Review of Related Literature

3.1 Professional Development

Education is a motivational way that teaches the application of learned knowledge (Bandura, 1997). The schooling of a child depends upon the motivation and hardworking of a teacher. Teacher motivates them to concentrate on the subject and helps them to deal with the subject matter knowledge. According to Jimmy (2013) education is not only the way to gain knowledge but it teaches to act on the learned words. A child can learn more than 80% of its learning at schooling age. Henry (2009) stated that people are known by their actions and if a teacher is confronting teaching issues than how a student would put learning into acting? In institutions, teacher is the only subject who have to work on students' learning by his/her actions and also use this demonstration in the class to furnish learning environment of classroom. The concluding words of above ideas claims that teacher is a subject who can create all these abilities in students but for this development, he/she should be developed through workshops, training and like these activities to make sure the prosperous application in the classroom.

As reported by Field et al. (1994) that these skills can be learned by teachers through professional development and teacher's professional development can only be enhanced by solely demonstration, where teachers have to require diverse staff development opportunities in learning collaboratively so as to ameliorate the entire school. In addition to this, the duties of teachers reveal the same responsibility that they have to perform in classroom. It is also elucidated that the needy professionalism has to be achieved and balanced through additional professional input. Research concluded that the teaching has become the center of many critical thinkers sadly results have shown

that the teachers are in both type of sectors are unaware about the levels, limitation of learners and the utilization of their skills for the professional learning.

As Shulman and Shulman (2004) stated that humans are always in learning process. They learn from their siblings, from society and from the hurdles that they have to resolve. Likewise, the better learning place for teachers is classroom where they tackle sitting students having various learning ways. As reality, the learning criteria of teachers is vary from students, for instance, teachers learn through the teaching strategies to get information about how to increase the cognitive and perceiving senses of students and these both skills are only ways to make better the learning performance of learners. For the development of professionalism in teachers, it would be better to offer more and more varieties of effective training and workshops to them. Meaningful learning is not easy to achieve at initial times, but it requires sometimes with a slow process to ascertain all helpful ways in the learning of information for both teachers and students. Furthermore, studies have also underlined that the better professional development of instructors serves to increase the success of learners, which is most important component that children need to move towards success. According to some extents, including the report of European Commission (2008) that the 90% of students' success and score depend on the quality of teacher. It has also been noted that teachers should be well-prepared while disseminating knowledge to students as well as have skills to observe whether students are receiving the disseminated information or not.

According to Hopkins, Ainscow and West (1994) that the curriculum and its designed ways instruction are helpful to create the teaching abilities in teacher as well as learning abilities with keen learners, regarding effective continuous professional development (CPD) and educational environment at schools. Meiers and Beavis (2005) argued that the role of teacher is an important aspect of students' educational life, where teacher's teaching should be noteworthy, and it's momentous for teacher to comply with the characteristics and importance of school context and these are important component for effective continuous professional development (CPD). It is a substantial level of professional platform that adjoins the curriculum, instruction, and teachers. Importantly, teaching norms require some aspects from a teacher, including enough time to perceive the needs of learners, go through from creative thinking perspective and teacher should know that what students are doing and what they have to do, and what should be placed, where all the applicable visions and missions related with the expected signs of teacher's value and professional development can be easily and successfully achieved by a teacher. In short, the significant, positive correlations between teacher quality and student achievement, as most important within-school factors explaining performance, and between in-service training and student outcomes, are consistently borne out by research. The European Union (EU), focusing on high quality teaching as key prerequisite for high quality education and training, highlights the school's duty to provide young citizens a circumstance with the competencies that they need to adapt to be globalized and a complex environments, where creativity, innovation, initiative, entrepreneurship and commitment to continuous learning areas that are as important as knowledge. In

particular, promoting the development of teachers' competence in teaching transversal competences and heterogeneous classes, and collaborating with colleagues and parents, are seen as essential. All the highlighted ideas are the main pillars in professional development that are being taught by repeated training and the favourable environment.

3.2 Continuous Professional Development

Although the complexities of the teaching profession require a lifelong learning perspective for opting abrupt educational changes and evolving constraints or need. International studies on teachers and their professional development have shown that so far, in-service training is considered as a professional duty in about a half of all European states, but it is in practice optional in many of them. Incentives to encourage participation in continuous professional development (hereafter CPD) appear few, and penalties for no participation are rare. In accordance with the degree of centralization/decentralization in national education systems, the responsibility for planning and organizing CPD, falls to schools or local authorities in a certain number of countries.

The forms of support to teachers' professional development can consist in paid working time and substitutions (often discouraged for budget and organizational reasons), funding of CPD costs sustained by teachers, salary incentives, CPD as condition for salary progression and promotion, national policies and campaigns (such as the recent one in Punjab). An organized plan of support measures for new teachers in the first years of their career - the most demanding and decisive stage of teachers' development is foreseen in only a small group of EU countries, among which the UK, Luxembourg and Lithuania seem to have a wide range of support activities.

The form, content and context conditions of teachers' professional development (CPD) are extensively described and analyzed in OECD's recent TALIS survey, focused on fostering educational performance and effectiveness, outlining key variables for effectiveness in teachers. The survey, which is based on the perceptions and self-reports of lower secondary education teachers, points out that CPD activities appear to be relatively loosely linked with school practices in the areas of instruction, evaluation of outcomes and giving feedback if needed, and school leadership; this seems to recommend policies aimed at a stronger integration of different functional domains of schooling. In the following literature review, professional development is defined, in accordance with the perspectives of several studies taken into account by the TALIS survey, as related to activities developing an individual's skills, knowledge, expertise and other characteristics as a teacher (excluding Initial Teacher Education).

As Clarke and Hollingsworth (2002) stated that literature on educational effectiveness seems to outline a conceptual framework that can be described as an 'onion-rings model' going from the micro-level to the macro-level perspective – with individual teachers personal characteristics (competences, beliefs and attitudes) at the core, a second layer concerning teaching effectiveness in the classroom (instructional repertoires), a further layer about teachers' cooperation in school contexts, and finally considering

national policies and organizational features (including issues of autonomy, accountability, evaluation in education systems) as the final and an important outer layer.

According to Richardson and Placer (2001) the literature mentioned here focused mainly on policy-amenable effectiveness features, considering the most favorable conditions for teachers' professional learning, above all in school contexts as professional communities. Such a perspective takes stock of past failures of CPD programmer informed by a deficit-mastery model, consisting in 'one-shot' professional development approaches, adopting instead a 'change as professional learning' perspective, inspired by adult learning and situated cognition theories, according to the paradigm of the teacher as reflective practitioner, taking responsibility for learning to improve the quality of professional performance. A shift can therefore be distinguished from a technical-rational-top-down approach to CPD, towards a more cultural-individual interactive approach to the professional development of teacher so that same could be transferred to the professional learning of students.

Since not all the learning of teachers promotes professional development in practice and school improvement, existing literature gives some indications about key professional learning activities that enable teachers to tackle rapid changes: keeping updated; experimentation; reflective practice; knowledge sharing; innovation, engaging students in practical work, encouraging them to ask questions and injecting a perspective of creativity. As regards conditions affecting teacher learning, two theoretical perspectives are usually taken into account: psychological factors (teacher cognition and motivation plus understanding students); organizational factors (leadership, teacher collaboration, staff relationships and communication, locus of control, opportunities for teachers' learning and friendly relationship with students). The latter factors are considered as prerequisites for linking teacher professional development and school development with the learning development of students. The second theoretical perspective often refers to system theory on change, linking structural, cultural and political dimensions of school workplace environments to professional learning.

However, researchers warn about the need for more rigorous and robust evidence for the claim that CPD in schools sustains improvement and student learning enhancement, since the knowledge base on conditions for teacher learning in the workplace appears fragmentary and heterogeneous for concepts, methods and instruments, thus increasing the difficulty of testing complex multi-level models about the impact of teacher learning and teaching dimensions. The results can be considered as inconclusive, apart from a few findings. Autonomy and decentralization seem to work better for student results if coupled with external exit examinations. That is, accountability system snatched with devolution seem to have positive effects on outcomes; moreover, schools' responsibility in hiring staff may influence the quality of schooling. Likewise, the subjects should be divided as the capabilities of teachers not by their teaching experience.

Recent studies concerning (European Union, 2007) the status of professional learning in the US have also explored the ways in which policy can affect professional

learning, taking four high-performing states (Vermont, Missouri, New Jersey and Colorado) as examples, selected on the basis of high levels of teacher participation in CPD, research-consistent policies, and student achievement improvements, but characterized by geographic, demographic and policy context diversity. A wide, all-encompassing conceptualization of teacher learning and development within communities and contexts is offered by Shulman and Shulman (2004) that it includes the key elements of vision, motivation, understanding, practice, reflection and community. For instance, involvement of community in school environment, parental collaboration with the teachers and the most requisite is parent meetings where a father/mother can easily discuss the loopholes of his/her child with the teachers; considering fact that a child spends only few hours at school but a big time at home.

The findings presented here come from studies which mostly conceptualize teacher learning and development as a process of active individual construction and acculturation into social practices – linked to changes in participation in socially organized activities, and to individuals – use of knowledge as an aspect of their participation in social practices to pay his/her social role. However, the following overview of findings also takes into account the perspectives of evaluation of literature and impact studies; in that they can contribute to understanding features of professional development can actually make a difference but by considering demographic evaluation.

As Little (2003) distinguishes between professional learning and professional development, which often appear distinct in theory and practice. If professionals learn from experience and that learning is ongoing through active engagement in practice, professional development features and delivery have often appeared at odds in several countries and realities so far, extracting professionals from their key professional learning environments (schools and classrooms) and assuming that experts know best what contents and kind of professional development teachers need.

According to Seago (2004), in contrast with traditional CPD perspectives, teacher professional learning is now mostly conceptualized in the literature as dynamic, ongoing, continuous, and set in teachers' daily lives and embedded in the classroom context and constructed through experience and practice. The collective participation of teachers from the same department, grade or subject is more likely to be coherent with their experiences, afford opportunities for active learning, and contribute to a shared professional culture – the development of a common understanding of instructional goals, methods, problems and solutions. According to recent research, teachers agreed that the most popular long-term professional development activities were peer observation what and how they learn and sharing practice if they feel hurdles in above areas.

Darling-Hammond and Richardso (2009) cleared that teaching as part of this model of professional learning; the importance of teacher collaboration comes to the fore. Traditionally, teaching is understood to be a 'uniquely isolated profession', nevertheless, teacher collaboration is identified by researchers and educators as one of the most relevant features of school culture in order to foster teacher learning, satisfaction and

effectiveness about students and the teaching subjects. Collaboration arising from deep, individual and continuous interest is clearly hard to achieve, requiring trust and risk taking; the de-privatization' of teaching implies changes of deeply-rooted norms, cultures and practices

As above arguments cleared that the relevance of teacher efficacy for teacher effectiveness, as related to powerful CPD experiences, ought also to be mentioned. The literature on the topic defines teacher efficacy as the teacher's self-assessment of one's own ability to support student learning; it is described as related to teachers' persistence facing obstacles in order to meet goals in their practice, as well as with the tendency to changing, taking risks and experimenting the teaching methodologies. The sources of teacher efficacy, the key ones appear to be mastery experiences (i.e. direct teaching experiences that are challenging but successful), together with vicarious experiences (observations of peers of similar ability levels, teaching challenging ideas successfully, jigsaw and discussion so that students share their views) and social/verbal persuasion (receiving positive feedback from students, peers and superiors).

Teacher efficacy is therefore strongly connected to teacher professional learning opportunities that can provide mastery and vicarious experiences, thus raising teachers' personal competence levels. School embedded professional learning opportunities can thus answer to self-directed desires for instructional change, which can then provide the motivation to sustain efforts and overcome obstacles. A key pocket of research, finally, has consistently linked teacher efficacy and student achievement, indicating the former as a reliable precursor to, and predictor of, the latter. There seems to be an indirect but powerful relationship between increasing teacher efficacy and increased student achievement; research theorizations indicate that teacher efficacy, mediated by contextual factors, impacts what teacher learn from CPD, and how they learn, with reciprocal and reverberating effects. Impact studies regarding teachers' high quality professional learning and development have by now reached a research-based (theoretical and empirical) consensus on the critical features of professional development those which make an activity effective for increasing teacher learning and changing practice, and ultimately for improving student learning.

According to Cohen and Hill (2000) there are at least five core features of effective professional learning and development, on which there is research consensus, stemming from a great number and diversity of studies (both case studies, large-scale and experimental research) conducted since 2000, with the proposal of a core conceptual framework for studying professional learning and development's impact on teachers and students. As Teddlie and Reynolds (2000) talked about the efforts to develop collaborative learning and working is often limited by individualistic and bureaucratic norms or structures in many contexts. Developing collaborative CPD i.e. building a professional learning community, appears a slow, demanding process characterized by conflicts and misunderstandings, where participants form a group identity with norms of interaction and shared responsibility for growth, learning to use difference and conflict

productively. Since the focus is on improving instructional practice, the identification of problems implies making one's teaching practice public and adopting an inquiry stance.

4. Research Methodology

4.1 Methods

This study used qualitative method, considered and assented as the best method for the deep understanding of any concerned gap as well as elucidated more tracts to know that what should have to do for a fruitful consequence of any subject or gap (Creswell 2007). As reality, this allow to find out the observations and personal views of participants about where is hurdle and how it could be tackled? Further, a friendly environment lets one to share his/her mental conditions aside fear etc. for that, the interviewed participant was engaged in discussion so that they could deliver an exact perspective about the discussed topic. Additionally, the participants were also interrogated through various complex inquiries so we can get a better comparison of the usage, background thinking, applicable methodology and impacts of professional development on students and get the hidden judgement of participants to investigate their views regarding professional development of teachers at secondary school level.

4.2 Data Collection and Analysis

The data was collected using semi-structured interviews. Researcher purposefully selected 6 public and private secondary schools for data collection. Total 13 participants participated in this study were participated from the secondary schools. The interviewed participants comprised of school stakeholders including Head Masters, Head Mistress, Senior and Junior teachers. Almost, the interviews schedules and timing were varying from one to another. Sometimes it ended in 20-25 minutes while, it took an hour in some areas. The participants' demographic information is shown in Table 1. The primary author of this study used qualitative tools of research to show the status-quo and status-quarry of teachers, schools and professional developmental strategies.

Table 1: Demographic Information of Interviewed Participants

Coded Name	Gender	Qualification	Teaching/Administrative Experience	Position
Head1	Female	M.Ed/MSc	More than 5	Head Mistress
SST2	Female	B.A/B.Ed	More than 3	SST (General)
JET3	Male	B.A/B.Ed	2 years	JET
Head4	Male	M.A/M.Ed	10 years	Head Master
Head5	Male	M.A/M.Ed	More than 7 year	Head Master
JET6	Female	B.A/B.Ed	4 years	JET
JVT7	Female	B.A	8 years	JVT
SST8	Male	B.A/B.Ed	More than 2	SST (General)
SST9	Male	MSc/B.Ed	2 years	SST (Science)
SST10	Female	MA.Ed	More than 15	SST (Science)
Head11	Female	MA/M.Phil	7 years	Head Mistress
JVT12	Female	MA/B.Ed	More than 6	JVT
JET13	Male	MSc/B.Ed	2 years	JET

Data was analyzed through thematic analysis. At initial stage, interviews were audio-recorded and then transcribed verbatim. Authors read and re-read the data, coded text. Data underwent categorization process and then thematicized accordingly (Creswell, 2011). In addition, collected data were fully escaped from all those detrimental facts which could have created loopholes for concerned participants. In some areas, the preferred participants' names were kept anonymous as their wish and their revealed perspective quoted as same what they had expressed during interviews.

6. Findings and Discussion

According to the Maria Montessori, researcher and educationalist, the Professional development can create a contributive positive school culture. Subjecting teachers to professional development courses should supply them with the tools, which they need to successfully approach with classroom challenges and grant them access to a professional community that can support their endeavors. Indeed, as humans are in learning process that shows that the Teachers are not fully perfect as they also have to learn from various aspects of knowledge. The evaluation or research work on professional development mostly does not approach learner's learning, in spite of learning vary kinds of teacher motivation, for instance, (attendance, learning activities) beside it, at worth, teacher transaction, such as (variety of information or classroom demonstration). But, unfortunately, the school at district level and administrating team do not separate among 'spending' and 'investing' in professional development (ECS, 1997). As this concept, the educational training, workshops and get to get gathering of professionals are best source to achieve the professional tools and their beneficial implementation in teaching. A recent report of the NCTAF (1996) identified two vital areas in learning. Firstly, the ability and experience of teachers is most critical aspect in learner's learning such as what to do when students don't acquire the delivered words? Whether they should be left without learning? Report concluded that the expert teachers who work in an ecosystem that permit students to understand bitterly and these are momentous key elements of prosperous learning and allows a sharing and receiving perspective among the students and teachers to resolve a self-created (from students when they don't want to learn). An interviewed principal of public school stated that:

"Professional development is not just revolving under of teaching skills but it includes several elements of individual's professional learning including; taking time to motivate towards success, follow through the recommendation of student and learning, to enhance the opportunities that induce students in participation and application of concerned knowledge in practical life which enhance their ability to recognize the learning needs and so on." (Interviewee Head 2)

Furthermore, he added that:

"We all people are unaware of these aspects and that is why, we people are still become black sheep in identifying the needs of learning and learners. That is reason, in which the professional development avails with teachers to get awareness of all these abilities as well as help them to get knowledge of how to apply these skills for the success of a learner."
(Interviewee Head 2)

As the perspective of Darling-Hammond (1998), the teacher abilities lay on knowledge of subject, enhancing student learning concept development, and teaching methods that shows his/her effectiveness. The broad-based research cited in the report, indicates that the conventional wisdom is wrong: anyone cannot teach, and teachers are not born (It is fact that the educational field is based on technical teachings which require from teacher first to understand and then deliver). But, it is a fact that the individuals are not the same in learning likewise some of them are adroit learner, while some of them are average, some are slow learner while some of them are hast in picking of knowledge. As these facts, it became a liability of teacher to understand the all sitting students; to know that what should be applied in ways for the explicitly of revealing knowledge, how to make successful to learning as well how to induce classroom environment on positive side plus what to do for creating learning interests in students. However, all these should be gained and applied by an instructor as the learning conditions of learners. By comparing the above specimens, the concluding remarks about district Khuzdar shows it an educational orphan, where teachers still don't aware about professionalism in teaching and its learning benefits.

A recent report on the science of learning from the National Research Council (NRC, 1999), commence by the assistance that the rules and regulations of learning are as momentous as educational law, that should be used and applied on all learners. The new principles of learning, summarized in the report, drawn a new studies of the learning process and the development of competent performance.

Interviewed participants' views were consistent with findings of previous research suggesting that the following factors are founded worth for the teaching carrier and proliferation of effective techniques including; the peer-networking mechanism, the guidance and counseling of teachers and coaching them in hard time, has proved the encasement of their professional development at schools and college. The following comments are referred to:

"When the teacher adopts same strategies than their teaching, these would be associated with such collective aids for learning including; conundrum of better demonstration, emboldening of educational desires and converting hard situation with easeful ways. Certainly, the aim of teacher should be to made easy information in a way, where this information forges more knowledge not to siege learner in divergence." (Interviewee JET 13)

As above findings, method of peer-coaching and the relationship between teachers, are only ways, which persuade them to prefer and adapt new strategies of instruction to complete the advancement of knowledge of teaching and learning. According to Darling-Hammond and Ball (1998) that many teachers must face their deeply held beliefs about learning and knowledge and should reconsider their assumptions about students. Most teachers, even if their beliefs are consonant with the new reforms, they can develop new ways of teaching and assessing their work through learning outcomes. Interviewee participants stated the situation in the following comments:

“Peer-coaching has many strategies of teaching, for instance, out-of-class activities, study groups and collaborative planning and in-class coaching activities such as peer-observation. (Interviewee Head 2)

“The teacher cooperation and collaboration are necessary for professional learning to occur. In addition, the successful implementation of this mechanism needs a close partnership among colleagues as well.” (Interviewee Head 11, SST 9)

Furthermore, many participants emphasized on the demonstration in learning. They focused that teaching should be student-center not merely adhere to teacher, owing to the entire education is based upon a child. Due to this fact, the interaction between teacher, subject and student itself be his centered so that they learn through their learning needs and interest. These criteria are revolved direct teaching and learning over time and chances to demonstrate and application of what have been learned to the context of teacher (Loucks-Horsley, Stiles, and Hewson, 1996). It is worth noting that teacher engages children in practical work that helps them to learn by their own perception and experience of learning. In classroom, children do not have to do easy things, but they have to make easy things that happen through hardworking and learning and it is the responsibility of teacher to guide them. Additionally, all in these techniques can only be learned through experience where teacher has to observe that what strategy can relate with the psyche of students that creates interest plus remove hurdles of learning. Now question here arises that what should be a strategy to understand that what learners require from their teacher? Whether, without professional development or teaching experience could it be possible? Surely, no. One interviewed respondent reported the utilization of technology in professional development and teaching as expressed:

“Technology can also be used for the purpose of improving professional development. For instance, video cameras can be used to promote self-assessment and for peer coaching. Electronic networking services provide rich databases for educators and e-mail and social networking sites can help teachers and administrators in connection with colleagues and to discuss the problems and suggest solutions. Teachers can use staff development

videotapes to improve their knowledge and skills. Thus, professional development has become an important part of learning.” (Interviewee Head 5, SST 10)

Participants were of their views that professional development has become an important part of learning and teachers have to learn these modern strategies and their usage to know that how much they can facilitate their students. Cohen and Hill (1998) explored the relationship between technologies and state policy, teacher learning, and student achievement. They suggested a model in which teacher knowledge, technological teaching and assessment practice were influenced when policy provides opportunity for teacher to be beneficial from professional development, in particular, professional development focused on the teachers to teach the designed curriculum to improve student performance. Furthermore, she pointed out miserable situation in the following comments:

“The education sector confronts various problems and issues such as shortage of funds, neglectivism, and corruption. These barriers have always stopped us to motivate our instructors towards professionalism as well as suppressed us to facilitate our learners with professional learning.” (Interviewee JVT 7, JET 6, Head 1)

Indeed, education is the process which induces people to learn from various aspects. These aspects can merely cover when the teacher has skills to reveal information in a way which can be clearly explain this knowledge. Teaching can be effective just by the proper application of teaching that knowledge and skills in the classroom. Majority of the interviewee respondents mentioned that:

“Education in Balochistan is worse by far to frequent and problem is not just to see this destruction but we have to prompt ourselves to cover this problem. As a head, I observed that we are lacking of teachers’ training and these training are only way to get rid of those worsen problem. We should create an environment to arrange training and engage our teachers in learning.” (Interviewee SST 2)

“Certainly, the education in Khuzdar is remained benignant of unskilled teachers, among those teachers, many of them are still do not know that how to develop their teaching skills and apply them while teaching. Well, it is fact that we are living in an age and era where many of us are unaware of our duties and responsibilities.” (Interviewee JET 13)

Another interviewed respondent responded that professional development organizes students and teachers too. It also underlines whether they are interested in teaching and learning of students or not, stated in detail:

“Professional development has made easy to recognize that how much a teacher is sane or which teacher has preferred teaching for. We use professional investigation from various

processes where we motivate teacher in front of their colleagues to answer what has been asked. This helps us in presumption about whether he is able to teach or not." (Interviewee JET 6)

"Lack of professionalism is just due to lack of interest in teaching, but through my experience, I guide all those teachers who are working under my subordination. He further added that he keeps personal meetings with instructors and guide them to comply with a prosperous way to meet the needs of teaching and students learning." (Interviewee Head 1, SST 2, JVT 12)

Furthermore, likewise one participant explained the importance of professional development for his teaching and expressed that:

"Professional development can only eradicate this pestilence from secondary learning institutions. It works like an action research, it identifies the weaknesses of teacher; while on the other hand, it works to get the reason and solution of this weakness in an effective way. Thankfully professional development is both proactive and responsive to change and is constantly evolving to deliver this great public service which has such an impact on the life chances of our children and young people who are considered as the constructor of the next generation of adults, employees and business men." (Interviewee SST 8, Head 5)

The most important is to build a bridge between the teaching and professional development and how it can be proved effective for instructional and learning platform. The success of standards-based reform depends on teacher's ability to foster basic knowledge, advanced thinking and problem solving among their students and such effective practices require teachers to have a deep understanding of the content which they teach to know that the characteristics of professional development have effects on teaching practice. Additionally, Professional development is considered an essential mechanism for deepening teachers' content knowledge and developing their teaching practices. As a result, professional development could be a cornerstone of systemic reform efforts designed to increase teachers' capacity to teach as what the standard are required in teaching (Loucks and Stiles, 1998).

The findings of the study also revealed that learning in classroom is not only related with reading, but communication skills are also an important part of learning. It is backbone of teaching. Its components have unique qualities, for instance, the reading and listening are receptive areas where students receive information from various perspective. While the writing and speaking are productive skills which induce students to reveal what information they have to share. In this circumstance, the production overlaps over reception. The students have to demonstrate the learned knowledge at any cost whether in class or in exam. It has been clearly elucidated that these communication skills consist of techniques through which teacher should have to teach his student in

order to deal, learn and utilize these skills to gain knowledge in both effective and useful way.

7. Conclusion and Recommendations

Summing up the study with conclusion and recommendations, it is prosperously apprehended that the professional development is the most effective and powerful technique to increase the interest and learner's achievements. It works to fulfill the learning requirement of students by completing their needs to meet with effective teacher through teaching. In contemporary epoch, previous educational system has fully been changed. For instance, in these days, education is based on varieties of knowledge and this knowledge could not be delivered just in a simple way but by the use of professional development and understanding of how to teach in a prosperous way. In addition, one of the most important part is teacher whose responsibility is to satisfy students as learning perspective. This underlined a meager spectacle of education, especially, the teachers' links with professional development. Because, a teacher is one who should know the skills to teach, the skills of handling students and the most important to deal with the abrupt questions, raised by students.

Furthermore, weighing up the nature, scope, impact and status of professional development, it is worthy to note that professional development is only way to get the fruits of education. Teachers should learn and use these skills to fulfill the requirements of their disciples and also identify the weaknesses of students through these abilities. While, educational policy makers it compulsory in curriculum that a teacher has to learn the skills of teaching every subject as its standard and for this conducting workshops, seminars and meeting with higher authority are mandatory. In this way, we can tackle the teaching problems at everywhere especially in the concerned district, Khuzdar. Further, it has also been observed that the teacher should know how to enhance and improve students' learning as well as what should be criteria to furnish them in each aspect of educational and professional life. In this circumstance of both teacher and students' needs, the professional development is one and everything that maintains the advancement of knowledge, teachers' abilities and students' professional life.

Adding more with concluded aspects of professional development, it has been enumerated that the education without use of professionalism is nothing. Education is influencing variation of information and this knowledge needs tact to disclose it in front of students. A teacher can easily succeed in it, but for it, instructors have to furnish themselves by the awareness of which area needs amelioration and what should be done for it unambiguously. Nevertheless, the following do down with participants and perception of researchers have cleared to overlap some aspects by suggesting suitable commendations.

Pulsing the recommendation with concerned discussion related with the various perspective of participants, in consequence, this theme has been achieved that the professional development becomes the need of teachers at both private and public

schools. Khuzdar, being a large district of Balochistan has been victimized of poor educational condition. These various observations have made it clear that there should be a specific formula which has to be implemented for enhancing these qualities in teaching profession. With this, the district educational authorities have responsibility to measure that whether the teachers are able to do this profession or deteriorating education therefore, there should be merit in selection. Furthermore, the teaching should be merged with professional development, for this it is very requisite to create such a working features, for instance, workshops, mentoring sessions, teachers training which could identify the contemporary feebleness with solution at the extent possibility. Also, it has become a liability of teacher to understand the all sitting students; to know that what should be ways for explicitly revealing knowledge, how to make successful learning occur as well as how to induce classroom environment positively? However, all these should be gained and applied by an instructor during lecture.

Finally, the professional development is not just under of teaching skills but it includes several elements of individual's professional learning including taking time to motivate towards success, follow the recommendation of student and learning, to enhance the opportunities that induce students in participation and application of concerned knowledge in practical life, enhance their ability to recognize the learning needs. The joining and selection of teacher should be run under specific criteria, where they have been observed by some special instants to know that whether they can be able to enhance the quality of teaching or not? This question can be enumerated by the strategy which foreign countries are transacting for the professional development of their teachers. This transaction has furnished their educational system and rewarded them skills to know the loopholes in education and cover them with possible solutions. All these can only be acquired when one state gets education as its weapon and spends more budgets on it instead of imposing it's all stamina on arsenals.

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